

Unlocking the potential of bacterioplankton-mediated microcystin degradation and removal: A bibliometric analysis of sustainable water treatment strategies

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ABSTRACT

Microcystins (MCs) constitute a significant threat to human and environmental health, urging the development of effective removal methods for these toxins. In this review, we explore the potential of MC-degrading bacteria as a solution for the removal of MCs from water. The review insights into the mechanisms of action employed by these bacteria, elucidating their ability to degrade and thus remove MCs. After, the review points out the influence of the structural conformation of MCs on their removal, particularly their stability at different water depths within different water bodies. Then, we review the crucial role played by the production of MCs in ensuring the survival and safeguarding of the enzymatic activities of *Microcystis* cells. This justifies the need for developing effective and sustainable methods for removing MCs from aquatic ecosystems, given their critical ecological function and potential toxicity to humans and animals. Thereafter, challenges and limitations associated with using MC-degrading bacteria in water treatment are discussed, emphasizing the need for further research to optimize the selection of bacterial strains used for MCs biodegradation. The interaction of MCs-degrading bacteria with sediment particles is also crucial for their toxin removal potential and its efficiency. By presenting critical information, this review is a valuable resource for researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders involved in developing sustainable and practical approaches to remove MCs. Our review highlights the potential of various applications of MC-degrading bacteria, including multi-soil-layering (MSL) technologies. It emphasizes the need for ongoing research to optimize the utilization of MC-degrading bacteria in water treatment, ultimately ensuring the safety and quality of water sources. Moreover, this review highlights the value of bibliometric analyses in revealing research gaps and trends, providing detailed insights for further investigations. Specifically, we discuss the importance of employing advanced genomics, especially combining various OMICS approaches to identify and optimize the potential of MCs-degrading bacteria.

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1. Introduction

Cyanobacteria and their associated toxins, particularly microcystins (MCs), pose a significant and escalating risk to human and animal health and the ecological balance of freshwater bodies worldwide (Chen et al., 2019). The proliferation of cyanobacterial blooms has become a growing concern due to their detrimental effects on water quality, aquatic biodiversity, and human well-being (Chen et al., 2019). These blooms can produce toxins, such as MCs, which can cause severe liver damage, respiratory problems, and even fatality in humans and animals (Huisman et al., 2018). Consequently, it is imperative to understand the underlying mechanisms driving cyanobacterial blooms and MC production, to develop effective ecosystem management and mitigation strategies.

Recent research has shed light on the microbial degradation of cyanobacteria and MCs, focusing on identifying and characterizing key microbial communities involved in this process (Dziallas and Grossart, 2011a; Li et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022a). The degradation of MC encompasses various pathways, including enzymatic and non-enzymatic degradation, needing the identification of MC-degrading genes and microorganisms to develop efficient bioremediation strategies (Zhang et al., 2018). Advanced analytical techniques like LC-MS/MS and NMR spectroscopy have investigated degradation pathways, its products and mechanisms associated with different MC variants (Jiang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). These approaches have identified specific enzymes involved in MC degradation, such as the carboxylesterase MlrA (Silva et al., 2023). Nonetheless, significant knowledge gaps remain regarding the microbial degradation of cyanobacteria and MCs, including the factors influencing degradation rates and impacts of environmental conditions on the associated microbial communities (Liu et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022b). Understanding the chemical conformational structures of MC variants and their effects on stability, toxicity, and degradability is also crucial. Specific amino acids, such as Adda and Mdha, are pivotal in MC toxicity and degradation (Rastogi et al., 2021). Moreover, proteomic studies have elucidated the regulation of MC biosynthesis in *Microcystis* (Hu et al., 2021b). Recent investigations indicate that the chemical structure of MCs influences their stability and degradation rates, with cyclic variants displaying better resistance to degradation than linear variants (Maghsoudi et al., 2016). These findings hold significant implications for the development of effective bioremediation strategies and the management of cyanobacterial blooms.

Metabolomic and genomic approaches have facilitated the study of cyanobacterial diversity, distribution, and genetic regulation of toxin biosynthesis in *Microcystis*. Environmental factors like light intensity and temperature as also reactive oxygen species (ROS), influence the genetic regulation of MC biosynthesis, impacting the expression of MC biosynthesis genes (Cai et al., 2021; Dziallas and Grossart, 2011b; Wang et al., 2021). Identifying cyanobacterial strains and their genetic diversity provides insights into their ecological niches and toxin production potential (Cheng et al., 2023). These approaches have also enhanced our understanding of the evolution and ecological success of the cyanobacterium *Microcystis* (Kakade et al., 2021; Watson et al., 2016). However, several research gaps remain, including the ecological impacts of cyanobacteria and MCs in marine environments and environmental factors influencing cyanobacterial blooms in various aquatic ecosystems (Chorus et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022c).

Research efforts have not only focused on *Microcystis* but also on microbial species involved in MC degradation. Metabolomic and genomic approaches have played a vital role in identifying and characterizing MCs-degrading genes, pathways, and microbial communities (Dziallas and Grossart, 2011a; Li et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2020). Understanding these microbial communities and their metabolic pathways provides valuable insights for developing effective bioremediation strategies and managing cyanobacterial blooms. Recent studies, have highlighted the influence of intracellular compounds released by

Microcystis on the microbial degradation of MCs, with some compounds serving as potential carbon sources for MCs-degrading microbes (Wei et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). These findings underscore the importance of considering both cyanobacterial host and their associated microbial community in developing efficient bioremediation strategies.

While significant progress has been made in unraveling the microbial degradation of cyanobacterial and MCs, including identifying communities, genes, and pathways involved, several gaps in knowledge persist. Factors influencing degradation rates and the impacts of environmental conditions on the microbial communities involved in degradation require further investigation (Zhang et al., 2022a). Additionally, understanding the ecological impacts of cyanobacteria and MCs in marine environments and the factors driving cyanobacterial blooms in different aquatic ecosystems remains a priority for future research (Koshigoe et al., 2023).

This study aims to understand cyanobacteria and MC dynamics in various aquatic systems comprehensively. It encompasses cyanobacteria's impacts on aquatic ecosystems, wildlife, and human health by critically analyzing the latest research on microbial degradation of cyanobacteria and MCs, reviewing the role of MC structures, and exploring advances in metabolomic and genomic approaches. Our study aims to identify key functional groups and molecular mechanisms within bacterioplankton communities capable of degrading cyanobacteria and MCs. Furthermore, the study reviews management strategies, highlights challenges and opportunities for integrating research on cyanobacteria and MC dynamics, ecology, genetics, and physiology, and explores emerging research questions and priorities to advance our understanding of these topics. Through bibliometric analyses, this review provides insights into the current state of research on cyanobacteria and MCs, identifying knowledge gaps and uncovering trends related to biodegradation and management strategies. Ultimately, we aim to develop effective interdisciplinary management strategies for controlling cyanobacterial blooms and MC contamination, addressing the needs of various stakeholders and ensuring the safety and quality of local to global water sources.

2. Bibliometric analysis of research on mc degradation and natural biotechnologies for water treatment: insights and trends from the web of science (1991–2023)

For a comprehensive understanding on research concerning MC degradation and natural biotechnologies for water treatment, we conducted a bibliometric analysis using data from the Web of Science Core Collection, including all editions, covering the years 1991 to 2023. Our analysis aimed to identify key research trends, collaboration patterns, and emerging topics within this field.

2.1. Dataset description

The study utilized a dataset consisting of 1514 documents gathered from 343 distinct sources, spanning the time frame from 1991 to 2023. It is worth noting that this dataset exhibited an annual growth rate of 12.43 %, indicating a consistent increase in research on the subject matter over the years. On average, the documents within this dataset were approximately 7.12 years old, implying that most were published around 2014. Furthermore, each document in this dataset received an average of 35.97 citations, underscoring their significant influence within the field. This dataset encompassed 2947 Keywords Plus (ID) and 3252 Author's Keywords (DE), offering a comprehensive overview of the primary themes and subjects addressed in the documents.

The corpus covered a wide array of document types, with articles being the most prevalent (1270), followed by reviews (137), proceedings papers (38), and various other types such as editorial material, meeting abstracts, and early access articles. Among the 4899 authors, 24 authors were responsible for single-authored documents. Collaboration

Fig. 2. Three Fields Plot Map analysis - network analysis of highly cited keywords, authors, and institutions in MC degradation and water treatment, with the darkness of the color bars representing the frequency of occurrence of each keyword, author, or institution, while the height of the bars reflects the relative importance or strength of the relationship between entities.

Fig. 3. Co-Authorship Network analysis of research on MC degradation and natural biotechnologies for water treatment - collaboration patterns between countries, visualized by circle size scale reflecting total number of publications and weighted by link strength, with a color scale score indicating research development from 2012 to 2020 and links representing collaborations.

in these regions. Furthermore, it should be noted that some countries like Germany, Australia, and Japan began researching the topic before others and have made significant strides in the field. On the other hand, countries like China and Brazil have recently gained new interest and are conducting more research in this area. However, some countries like Morocco show relatively low publication and citation rates. However, they display moderate total link strength, suggesting collaboration with other countries such as Portugal, Italy, Denmark, and Germany. These findings emphasize the potential for increased research collaboration and knowledge exchange to develop and implement practical solutions for MC degradation and nature-based biotechnologies for water treatment in Morocco and beyond. Data suggests a global interest in

exploring collaborative solutions to address the challenges associated with MC degradation and water treatment.

The coWord-Factorial analysis reveals key clusters of keywords in MCs degradation and water treatment, highlighting the primary research interests and interconnections in the research field. Specifically, our analysis shows that researchers focus on developing effective treatment processes for removing MCs from water sources. Additionally, they are exploring biodegradation methods to mitigate their harmful effects on lake ecosystems.

Two dimensions were identified. The first dimension emphasizes the importance of developing effective methods for removing MCs from water sources. This underscores the urgent need for practical solutions

to manage cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms and their impact on water sources and ecosystems. The second dimension highlights the need to understand the environmental impact of MCs. This dimension offers insights into the environmental implications of MCs and their effects on ecosystem sustainability.

The dimensions of the coWord-Factorial analysis provide a deeper understanding of the relationships between keywords in each cluster, which can inform future research directions and promote collaboration among researchers (Fig. 4).

The Choropleth Map analysis (Fig. 5) offers valuable insights into the interconnections among keywords about MC degradation and water treatment. One possible inference from the map is that researchers in this field are keenly interested in developing efficient techniques to eliminate cyanobacterial toxins from water sources. This can be observed by grouping keywords associated with cyanobacteria and their toxins, such as MCs, cyanotoxins, and cyanobacterial blooms.

Another noteworthy hypothesis is that research endeavors in this domain focus on enhancing water treatment processes' efficiency and effectiveness. The initial cluster of keywords concerning water treatment processes, including coagulation, flocculation, and disinfection by-products, supports this. Additionally, keywords related to ultrafiltration and powdered activated carbon suggest that researchers are exploring novel and innovative approaches to water treatment.

Lastly, the third cluster of keywords associated with lake ecosystems indicates that researchers are also investigating connections between MCs degradation and the well-being of these ecosystems. Keywords such as phytoplankton, eutrophication, and oxidation suggest that researchers might be studying the impact of MCs on lake ecosystems and how water treatment processes can be employed to enhance their health.

The Trend Topics analysis (Fig. 6) showcased the frequency and distribution of keywords over time in MCs degradation and water treatment. The most frequently occurring keywords were "microcystin" and "cyanobacteria," which focused on studying cyanobacteria and associated toxins, particularly MCs. Researchers also showed interest in removing MCs from water sources, improving water treatment processes, and studying the impact of MCs on lake ecosystems.

The analysis emphasized the need for continued research and collaboration to address critical research gaps. One of these gaps is the microbial degradation of MCs. Another gap is the need for more research on MCs-degrading bacteria for application in Multi-Soil-Layering (MSL)

technologies. While MSL technologies effectively remove MCs from water sources, more research is needed to study the effectiveness and performance of MCs-degrading bacteria in the lab and natural open-field settings. More research is needed to understand microbial degradation mechanisms and potential applications to develop more effective and sustainable solutions for managing harmful cyanobacterial algal blooms and their impact on water sources and ecosystems.

3. Reevaluating the role of MCs: protective adaptations of *Microcystis* for survival in changing environments

Contrary to the initial assumptions, the seemingly detrimental behavior of toxic *Microcystis* species, responsible for water bloom infestations by producing MCs, may be a strategic adaptation employed by these microorganisms to ensure their survival. MC production seems to be a vital and mandatory process for the persistence of *Microcystis* cells. These toxins may play a pivotal role in protecting and stabilizing crucial enzymes within the organism, thereby increasing its fitness, particularly under oxidative stress conditions (Dziallas and Grossart, 2011b; Spooft et al., 2020; Zilliges et al., 2011).

Notably, MCs bind to critical proteins involved in cellular processes. For instance, MCs form stable thioether bonds with cysteines of the large subunit of ribulose biphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (RuBisCO), which is a crucial enzyme involved in photosynthesis and carbon fixation (Zilliges et al., 2011). The binding of MCs to RuBisCO enhances under oxidative stress, suggesting that MCs can modulate protein activities. Furthermore, MCs bind to essential enzymes involved in energy metabolism, including glycolytic enzymes and the ATP synthase alpha subunit (Wei et al., 2016). This highlights the potential impact of MCs on cellular energy metabolism and, thus, growth.

Additionally, studies have observed significant changes in protein accumulation in the presence of MCs. For instance, a *Microcystis* mutant lacking MCs production capabilities (Dziallas and Grossart, 2011b) showed significant alterations in the accumulation of enzymes involved in the Calvin cycle, phycobiliproteins, and NADPH-dependent reductases when subjected to oxidative stress (Tonietto et al., 2012). These findings further highlight the importance of MCs in regulating cellular processes (Zilliges et al., 2011).

Finally, researchers have identified the 60 kDa chaperonin GroEL as a prominent MC-bound protein (Wei et al., 2016). GroEL is a molecular

Fig. 4. CoWord-Factorial analysis - identification of keyword clusters and their relationship to MCs degradation and water treatment.

Fig. 5. Choropleth Map analysis: global distribution of research publications on MC degradation and water treatment with three identified clusters - cyanobacteria and toxin elimination (Blue), water treatment processes (Red), and lake ecosystem impacts (Green) (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.).

Fig. 6. Trend Topics analysis - frequency and distribution of keywords over time in the research on MCs degradation and natural biotechnologies for water treatment.

chaperone that assists in protein folding and is involved in various cellular processes. The MC-GroEL complex forms when MCs bind to GroEL, enabling MCs to exploit GroEL's chaperone function, enhance their stability, and potentially protect *Microcystis aeruginosa*. This interaction prevents protein misfolding, promotes proper folding, and consequently bolsters the overall fitness of *Microcystis aeruginosa*.

Global warming and climate change have profound effects on various organisms. Abiotic factors such as non-optimal growth pH, high light intensity, and temperature impose stress on ancient cyanobacteria such as *Microcystis*. As a result of these stressors, oxidative stress is generated, damaging cellular components and generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Babica et al., 2006; Dziallas and Grossart, 2011b).

To counteract these effects, *Microcystis* has evolved adaptive mechanisms such as the secretion of toxins to ensure its survival and protect

its enzymatic activities (Zilliges et al., 2011). Yet, this adaptive strategy presents a paradoxical situation. While toxins produced by *Microcystis*, known as MCs, are effective in protecting the organism, they have deleterious effects on other organisms in contact with them, making *Microcystis* environmentally very unfriendly.

Microcystis has also developed antioxidant defense systems to mitigate ROS damage, including enzymatic and non-enzymatic mechanisms. Studies, such as those by Malanga et al. (2019), have demonstrated the effectiveness of these defense systems in protecting the organism from oxidative stress. However, it is essential to acknowledge the potential environmental impact of *Microcystis* and the harm it can cause to other organisms in aquatic ecosystems. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the balance between survival of *Microcystis* and its impact on the environment.

Ultimately, the production of MCs by *Microcystis* species, once perceived as detrimental behavior, is an indispensable and adaptive survival mechanism. The stressors associated with climate change force these microorganisms to develop sophisticated strategies involving toxins secretion. Nevertheless, the unintended consequences of MC exposure pose significant challenges for organisms and ecosystems. Unraveling the complexity of these interactions not only provides insights into the adaptations of ancient cyanobacteria to changing environmental conditions but also sets the stage for exploring cyanobacterial MC production and understanding their stability (Dinh et al., 2021; Herrera et al., 2023; Mazur and Pliński, 2001).

4. Understanding *Microcystis* and toxin dynamics: exploring mc production, stereochemistry, stability, toxicity, and environmental implications from genomics to metabolomics

4.1. A holistic approach: integrating genomic insights and metabolomics for understanding toxin production in *Microcystis*

Microcystis, a genus of freshwater cyanobacteria, is known for its prolific production of microcystins (MCs), i.e. cyclic peptides notorious for their toxicity. The intricate biosynthetic pathway involves a suite of genes, namely *mcyA*, *mcyB*, *mcyC*, *mcyD*, *mcyE*, *mcyG*, *mcyH*, and *mcyJ*, meticulously identified and characterized in various *Microcystis* strains (Kellmann et al., 2008; Rantala et al., 2004).

MC biosynthesis in cyanobacteria, particularly in *Microcystis aeruginosa*, follows a modular polyketide synthetase (PKS)/non-ribosomal peptide synthetase (NRPS) pathway (Christiansen et al., 2003; Dittmann et al., 2013; Kunyavskaya et al., 2021; Nishizawa et al., 2000; Noguchi et al., 2009; Pearson et al., 2004; Rantala et al., 2004). Within this pathway, NRPS activates and links amino acids, while PKS iteratively adds polyketide chains, resulting in the formation of the cyclic heptapeptide backbone characteristic of MCs (Dittmann et al., 2015).

The *mcyA* gene plays a crucial role by encoding an adenylation domain within the NRPS module. This domain activates and selects specific amino acids for incorporation into the MC molecule. Simultaneously, the *mcyB* gene encodes a condensation domain within the NRPS module, facilitating the stepwise elongation of the peptide backbone by linking activated amino acids together.

The *mcyC*, *mcyD*, and *mcyE* genes encode tailoring enzymes that introduce modifications to the MC molecule. These enzymes work in conjunction with the PKS and NRPS modules to enhance structural diversity. For example, methyltransferases encoded by *mcyC* and *mcyD* genes add methyl groups to specific positions within the MC backbone, while oxidases and reductases encoded by *mcyE* modulate oxidation and reduction reactions, respectively (Rantala et al., 2004). This intricate biosynthetic process, detailed by Tillett et al. (2000) and Tanabe et al. (2007), generates a spectrum of MC congeners with varying toxicities and stability.

The *mcyG* gene, encoding a methyltransferase, adds methyl groups to specific amino acids within the MC molecule, further enhancing structural diversity by modifying both the peptide backbone and side chains (Rantala et al., 2004). Epimerization domains introduce stereochemical variations, while thioesterase domains, as described by Rouhiainen et al. (2004), play a role in catalyzing the release of the completed MC from the PKS/NRPS assembly line.

The *mcyH* gene is involved in the cellular export of MCs, encoding an ABC transporter protein that facilitates the efflux of MCs from the cell (Gegotek and Skrzydlewska, 2023; Nishizawa et al., 2000; Pearson et al., 2004; Rantala et al., 2004). This prevents self-toxicity and allows the controlled release of toxins into the surrounding environment.

Finally, the *mcyJ* gene is thought to be involved in the regulation of MC biosynthesis. While its precise role is not fully understood, it likely contributes to the control of gene expression within the biosynthetic pathway or modulates the activity of enzymes involved in MC production (Tillett et al., 2000). The collaborative function of these genes

coordinates the intricate synthesis and regulation of MCs, unveiling the intricate complexity of MC production by *Microcystis* across diverse environmental conditions.

Metabolomic studies, employing advanced GC-MS analysis, unveil the intricate metabolic consequences induced by MC-LR. These studies expose metabolic disorders and mitochondrial dysfunction in HepG2 cells, triggered by the toxic peptide (Campos and Vasconcelos, 2010; Ma et al., 2017; McLellan and Manderville, 2017; Yang et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2021). MC-LR disrupts the cellular metabolism by affecting amino acid, lipid, and carbohydrate pathways, leading to an energy imbalance (Li et al., 2020a). Mitochondrial dysfunction arises from inhibited ATP production, increased reactive oxygen species, and oxidative stress (Wei et al., 2016). Additionally, the toxin disrupts protein phosphatases, notably PP1 and PP2A, perturbing protein phosphorylation and dephosphorylation processes (Falfushynska et al., 2021). This interference leads to dysregulated signaling pathways, including protein kinase C (PKC) and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), initiating inflammation and cytokine production (Chu et al., 2022; MacKintosh et al., 1990). Moreover, MC-LR induces apoptosis through caspase activation, mitochondrial membrane disruption, and cytochrome release, culminating in its toxic effects in HepG2 cells (Christen et al., 2013; Krishnan et al., 2020).

Furthermore, metabolomic analyses extend to potential biosynthetic pathways of secondary metabolites in distinct *Microcystis aeruginosa* strains, revealing the diversity of metabolomes shaping the cyanobacterial metabolic landscape (Massey and Yang, 2020; Steffen et al., 2014). When *Microcystis aeruginosa* is exposed to triclosan, a metabolomic analysis unveils alterations in potential metabolic pathways and their regulatory dynamics, showcasing the sensitivity of the cyanobacterial metabolome to environmental perturbations (Bukowska et al., 2018).

The molecular mechanisms underlying the evolution and diversification of MC biosynthetic pathways have also been investigated (Dittmann et al., 2013; Shishido et al., 2013). Studies found that horizontal gene transfer played a vital role in the evolution and diversification of MC biosynthetic pathways in *Microcystis* (Dittmann et al., 2015; Sun et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2020). The prevalence of transposable elements in toxic strains of *Microcystis* suggests a crucial involvement in genetic rearrangements, influencing the evolutionary dynamics associated with toxin production (Micallef et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2012b; Yuan et al., 2020; Zhang and Zhang, 2020). This heightened genetic diversity, facilitated by horizontal gene transfer, plays a significant role in regulating genes within toxin production pathways, leading to the observed upregulation or downregulation effects (Lin et al., 2011; Micallef et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2012b; Yuan et al., 2020; Zhang and Zhang, 2020). This intricate interplay underscores the adaptive mechanisms of *Microcystis*, offering valuable insights into the evolutionary dynamics governing its capacity for toxin synthesis.

4.2. Deciphering MC stereochemistry, stability, toxicity, and environmental implications

The stability of MCs is a crucial factor in their environmental persistence and toxicity. Studies revealed that the chemical structure of the amino acids in the MC molecule (Fig. 7), particularly those in the X and Z positions, plays a significant role in determining the variation and nomenclature of the molecule. This has led to the identification of 279 MC congeners to date (Bouaïcha et al., 2019).

The toxicity of MCs is closely associated with the side chain of Adda, which contains a double bond at position 6 (Pearson et al., 2010; Rinehart et al., 1994). The authors have highlighted the significance of the stereochemistry of this double bond, as it is typically in the E configuration of the toxic structure. In contrast, the Z configuration renders the molecule non-toxic. Furthermore, structural variations, such as methylation and demethylation of Me-Asp3 and Mdha7 acids or esterification of glutamic acid at position 6, influence the toxicity and

Fig. 7. Structural representation and stereochemistry of MC with variable amino acids X and Y at positions 2 and 4, and visual indication of the separation of the 7 amino acids with green bars. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

lipophilicity of different MCs (Bouaïcha et al., 2019). Moreover, the dextrogyre (D) and levogyre (L) forms of amino acids, including alanine (Ala) and methyl aspartic acid (Me-Asp), not only significantly contribute to the toxicity of MCs but also play a pivotal role in the recognition of MCs by their degrading enzymes, owing to the presence of steric hindrance. The persistence of MCs in the environment can be attributed to their high chemical stability, as well as their relatively good solubility in water (Lahti et al., 1997). Understanding the relationship between the stereochemistry of MCs and their stability is critical to developing effective strategies to mitigate their environmental impact and prevent human and animal exposure to these toxins.

Other studies have focused on how modifications to the MC molecule affect its stability. For instance, the replacement of the N-methyldehydroalanine residue at position 7 with N-methyldehydrobutyrine increased the stability of MC-LR ((Feng et al., 2023; Sanseverino et al., 2017). Similarly, Harada et al., al.(1996) found that replacing the l-arginine residue at position 4 with l-homoarginine increased MC-LR stability.

The conformational structure of MCs is also known to affect their stability. For example, the presence of d-Asp3 in MC-ADDA (MC-ADDA) results in a more stable and rigid conformation, leading to increased toxicity compared to other variants (Annala et al., 1996; Jaeger-Honz et al., 2022; Namikoshi et al., 1993). Similarly, leucine in position two of MC-LR enhances its stability and binding affinity to protein phosphatases, leading to increased toxicity compared to other variants (Takai et al., 2000).

The stability of MCs can also be influenced by environmental factors, such as temperature, pH, and sunlight (Santos et al., 2020). Likewise, temperature and alkaline conditions can also increase MC-LR degradation in water (Shimizu et al., 2011). Similarly, Xian et al. (2023) reported that UV radiation can induce MC-LR degradation in surface waters.

Toxicity of MCs is mainly attributed to their ability to inhibit protein phosphatases in the liver of higher organisms, leading to liver damage and cell death. The molecular mechanisms underlying the interactions between MCs and their target proteins and enzymes have been extensively studied. For example, MCs bind specifically to the catalytic subunits of PP1 and PP2A through their Adda residue, forming a covalent bond with a cysteine residue at the enzyme's active site (Fu et al., 2023; Jaeger-Honz et al., 2022; MacKintosh et al., 1990; Takai et al., 2000). This covalent bond prevents the dephosphorylation of proteins, leading to the accumulation of phosphorylated proteins and cell death (Moreno et al., 2019).

MC release and transport by *Microcystis* cells are complex processes

influenced by various factors, such as environmental conditions, cell density, and nutrient availability (Chen et al., 2019). For example, high nutrient availability can stimulate *Microcystis* cell growth and increase MC production and release (Paerl and Otten, 2016). Changes in environmental conditions, such as temperature and pH, can also affect the efficiency and specificity of intracellular compound release (Gu et al., 2023; Park et al., 2001; Zhang et al., 2022d). Other compounds in the environment, such as dissolved organic matter (DOM), can also affect the transport and uptake of MCs by other organisms (Gong et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021).

Recent studies have also highlighted the potential role of MC variants in regulating cyanobacterial blooms and their interactions with other organisms in aquatic ecosystems (Jaeger-Honz et al., 2022). MC-LR has been shown to induce gene expression in the cyanobacterium *Dolichospermum (Anabaena)* sp. 90 and promote the growth of the diatom *Asterionella formosa* (Dziallas and Grossart, 2011b; Paerl and Otten, 2016; Wei et al., 2023). These findings suggest that MC variants may have complex ecological functions beyond their toxicity to humans and animals.

In addition to their effects on human and animal health, MC contamination can have significant economic impacts. MC contamination can lead to the closure of recreational water bodies, such as lakes and rivers, and the loss of revenue from the tourism and fishing industries (Paerl and Otten, 2016). MC contamination can also affect the quality of drinking water and increase the costs of water treatment and management (Huisman et al., 2018; Massey and Yang, 2020; Schreidah et al., 2020). Therefore, effective management and mitigation strategies for cyanobacterial blooms and subsequent MC contamination are crucial to protecting human health and the environment and maintaining sustainable economic development.

Overall, gaining insight into the environmental adaptations of cyanobacteria through MC production, stability, and toxicity can offer cues for safeguarding against toxic cyanobacterial blooms. Notably, exploring MC degradation mechanisms provides a promising avenue for achieving this goal.

5. Exploring MC biodegradation: integrating metabolomic, genomic insights, and environmental influences

5.1. Unraveling enzymatic and non-enzymatic pathways and identifying key degrading genes

The breakdown of MCs is primarily orchestrated by microorganisms, specifically bacteria and fungi, which utilize these compounds as sources of carbon and energy (Cai et al., 2021; Cheng et al., 2021; Ding et al., 2022; Dziallas and Grossart, 2011a; Santos et al., 2021). Key players in this degradation process include bacterial taxa like *Sphingomonas*, *Sphingopyxis*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Aeromonas*, *Bacillus*, *Novosphingobium*, *Sphingobium*, possessing specific enzymes crucial for degrading MCs and other cyanobacterial metabolites (Falda et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2020; Lukhele and Msagati, 2023; Van Le et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2023).

The complex process of MC degradation involves multiple steps and enzymes, notably the *mtrABCD* genes responsible for initiating MC degradation (Huang et al., 2016; Krausfeldt et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2021; Zeng et al., 2021). Understanding the role of *mtrABCD* genes is pivotal for comprehending the catabolic processes involved in MC degradation.

The *mtr* gene cluster serves as a fundamental player in the degradation of MCs, orchestrating a sequence of crucial steps in their enzymatic breakdown. This cluster, consisting of *mtrA*, *mtrB*, *mtrC*, and *mtrD* genes, assigns unique and indispensable roles to each gene during the degradation process (Maghsoudi et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2020).

One key component, *mtrA*, encodes microcystinase, a specialized enzyme pivotal in initiating the degradation of MCs. Microcystinase plays a central role by cleaving specific peptide bonds within the MC molecule. For instance, in the bacterium *Sphingopyxis* sp. C-1,

microcystinase efficiently cleaves the Adda-Arg-peptide bond of MC-LR, leading to its subsequent breakdown (Bourne et al., 2001).

Facilitating the transportation of MC into bacterial cells, the *mtrB* gene is vital for subsequent enzymatic reactions within the bacterial cytoplasm (Shimizu et al., 2012). Simultaneously, *mtrC* encodes enzymes responsible for further cleavage of the MC molecule, breaking it down into smaller, less toxic fragments (Jin et al., 2022). Lastly, *mtrD* assumes a regulatory role, overseeing the expression of other *mtr* genes and ensuring their coordinated activity during MC degradation (Li et al., 2014).

The linearization of MCs by microcystinase, followed by their breakdown into non-toxic small peptides by other enzymes encoded by the *mtrABC* gene cluster, is summarized in Fig. 8. Additionally, other enzymes, such as carboxypeptidases, proteases, and peptidases, have also been shown to play a role in MC degradation (Dziga et al., 2013a; Wang et al., 2019).

In-depth research conducted by Ding et al. (2018), Xu et al. (2019b), and Liu et al. (2022) on the *mtr* gene cluster in *Sphingopyxis* sp. USTB-05 revealed an upregulation of *mtrA*, *mtrB*, and *mtrC* when exposed to MC-LR. This upregulation indicated the activation of the *mtr* gene cluster, resulting in the efficient degradation of MC-LR. These findings underscore the critical role of the *mtr* gene cluster in responding to and efficiently degrading specific MC variants.

Recent investigations by Liu et al. (2022), Sun et al. (2021), and Zeng et al. (2021) provided detailed insights into the intricate regulatory mechanisms controlling the *mtr* gene cluster. These studies highlight the impact of MC concentrations and environmental conditions on the transcriptional activation of *mtr* genes, revealing adaptive strategies employed by microorganisms in varying MC environments.

Moreover, the regulation of the *mtr* gene cluster is not solely influenced by MCs; environmental factors such as temperature, pH, and nutrient availability also play crucial roles. Several studies demonstrated that these factors significantly impact the efficiency of enzymatic degradation pathways based on the stereoisomeric configurations of MCs (Morón-López et al., 2020; Schreidah et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2014). Additionally, physiological factors of bacteria, including cell density, growth rate, metabolism, and stress response, can substantially influence the efficiency and specificity of degradation pathways (Hu et al., 2021a; Krausfeldt et al., 2019; Saito et al., 2003).

Bacterial extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) are instrumental in cyanotoxin breakdown within cyanobacterial blooms. Through adhesive properties, EPS bind and sequester cyanotoxins, reducing their availability and potential harm. EPS house diverse enzymes, including proteases and lipases, capable of degrading cyanotoxins, contributing to detoxification (Le et al., 2022; Ye et al., 2020). Moreover, EPS act as a

nutrient source, supporting the growth of bacteria within the bloom, enhancing cyanotoxin degradation. Interactions facilitated by EPS create a complex microbial community, fostering the establishment and growth of toxin-degrading bacteria, thereby promoting efficient cyanotoxin breakdown (Duan et al., 2023; Le et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2014, 2013; Ye et al., 2020).

Another area of investigation focuses on the role of bacterial quorum sensing in cyanobacterial blooms. Quorum sensing is a mechanism involving the production and detection of signaling molecules by bacterial cells, enabling effective communication and coordination of their behavior (Lamas-Samanamud et al., 2023; Zeng et al., 2021, 2020). Studies have demonstrated that quorum sensing can regulate the growth, metabolism, and cyanobacterial toxin. Specifically, in the case of cyanobacterial blooms, quorum sensing has been found to regulate the expression of the *mtr* gene cluster responsible for MC degradation (Lamas-Samanamud et al., 2023; Zeng et al., 2021). This regulatory mechanism involves the binding of quorum-sensing molecules, such as N-acyl homoserine lactones (AHLs) and autoinducer-2 (AI-2), to specific receptors. This binding triggers a signaling cascade that leads to the expression of the *mtr* genes. The quorum sensing pathway thus plays a significant role in the degradation of cyanotoxins and the regulation of cyanobacterial populations (Braun and Bachofen, 2004; Herrera and Echeverri, 2021; Kokarakis et al., 2023; Lamas-Samanamud et al., 2022).

While enzymatic pathways are the primary mode of MC degradation by microorganisms, non-enzymatic mechanisms, such as oxidation, hydrolysis, and photolysis, have also been shown to play a role in the breakdown of MCs (Moreno et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2023). Even living organisms, atop physical and chemical processes, may mediate these non-enzymatic pathways. For example, ROS generated by photosynthesis or environmental stress can oxidize MCs, leading to their degradation (Feng et al., 2023). Hydrolysis under acidic or alkaline conditions can also lead to the breakdown of MCs (Wang et al., 2024). Photolysis under UV light has been shown to be effective in degrading MCs in surface waters and can be enhanced by the presence of dissolved organic matter (DOM). However, this process may be less efficient in turbid waters with limited light penetration, and it may not be as practical for in-situ remediation compared to biodegradation. Biodegradation relies on a diverse array of microorganisms that inhabit various levels of the water column, making it a more versatile and feasible approach (Kennedy et al., 2023; Xie et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2023).

5.2. Microbial communities involved in MC degradation

Metagenomic and 16S rRNA gene sequencing approaches have been employed to identify the diversity and distribution of MC-degrading bacteria in various environmental settings, including freshwater lakes, rivers, and reservoirs. These techniques have revealed that Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes, and Actinobacteria dominated most MC-degrading bacterial communities and that these communities showed changes in functional diversity in response to environmental changes (Krishnan et al., 2020; Maruyama et al., 2003; Qin et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2021). A wide range of species capable of degrading MCs have been reported, including the most frequently encountered genera, *Sphingomonas* and *Sphingopyxis* (Dziallas and Grossart, 2011a; Dziga et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2021; Xu et al. 2019a), as well as *Bacillus* sp., *Arthrobacter* sp., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Novosphingobium* sp., *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, *Hyphomicrobium aestuarii*, *Sphingobium* sp., *Acinetobacter* sp., *Aeromonas* sp., *Rhodococcus* sp., *Ochrobactrum* sp., *Pseudoxanthomonas* sp., *Rhizobium* sp., *Steroidobacter* sp., and *Sphingonissella microcystivorans* (Kumar et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2023; Lukhele and Msagati, 2023; Maruyama et al., 2006; Salter et al., 2021; Sumaiya Idroos et al., 2017; Zeng et al., 2021).

Moreover, recent studies have shown that *Microcystis aeruginosa* can release organic carbon and nitrogen compounds that promote the growth of MC-degrading bacteria, leading to increased efficiency in MC

Fig. 8. Biodegradation pathway of MC-LR by MtrABC enzymes and associated bioproducts: illustration of the stepwise cleavage of the cyclic peptide structure and identification of critical intermediates - the red numbers from 1 to 7 represent the relative positions of the amino acids in the cyclic structure of the MC-LR molecule.

degradation (Christoffersen et al., 2002; Silva and Pernthaler, 2019; Song et al., 2019). While this may seem counterproductive for *Microcystis*, the release of these compounds and toxin production may have mutualistic and regulatory benefits (Dziallas and Grossart, 2011b).

On a mutualistic level, MC-degrading bacteria may benefit from *Microcystis aeruginosa* by feeding on the cyanobacteria's N-rich organic compounds and MCs released. In turn, *Microcystis aeruginosa* may benefit from the increased efficiency in MC degradation, which can help regulate the proportion of environmental toxins and prevent harmful concentrations from forming. This mutualistic interaction is likely a complex and multifaceted process involving both the release of organic compounds by *Microcystis aeruginosa* and MC-degrading bacteria's growth and metabolic activity. Furthermore, the regulatory benefits of this interaction may be supported by studies that have found relatively low concentrations of MCs in natural water samples, less than $10 \mu\text{g MCs L}^{-1}$, despite the occurrence of harmful algal blooms (Ge et al., 2021; Tito et al., 2022; Xue et al., 2023).

6. Understanding the transport and fate of cyanobacteria and MC in water columns: implications for bloom management

6.1. Physical processes influencing the transport of cyanobacteria and MC in water columns

Cyanobacteria and MCs can be transported over long distances in water bodies through physical processes such as diffusion, advection, and turbulent mixing (Ishikawa et al., 2002; Overman and Wells, 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). The fate of cyanobacteria and MCs in water columns is determined by several physical and chemical processes, including sedimentation, photodegradation, and hydrolysis (Gu et al., 2023; Schmidt et al., 2014; Xie et al., 2021). Additional elements that affect the movement and fate of cyanobacteria and MCs include water temperature, light intensity, the availability of nutrients, and water flow (Baer et al., 2023; Bretier et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2023).

6.2. Processes affecting the fate of cyanobacteria and MC in water columns

Their structural features influence the persistence of cyanobacteria and MCs in water columns. MC is a cyclic heptapeptide with specific amino acids, Adda and Mdha, that contribute to its toxicity and persistence (Paerl and Otten, 2013; Rastogi et al., 2021; Romanova et al., 2011). Conversely, dissolved organic matter (DOM) can potentially increase MC persistence in water columns (Christiansen et al., 2008; Wei et al., 2021). This occurs as DOM interacts with the toxin through hydrophobic interactions, making it less accessible to degrading microorganisms. However, *Microcystis aeruginosa* releases organic carbon and nitrogen compounds that can stimulate the growth of MCs-degrading bacteria, thus enhancing the efficiency of MC degradation (Lezcano et al., 2016; Silva and Pernthaler, 2019).

The dynamics governing the impact of organic matter on MC persistence reveal a nuanced interplay. On the one hand, dissolved organic matter (DOM) can potentially hinder the efficiency of MC degradation, resulting in elevated toxin concentrations and prolonged exposure for aquatic organisms. Concurrently, adsorption, a process where MC molecules adhere to DOM, exacerbates the enduring presence of MC in the environmental context. Conversely, the release of organic carbon and nitrogen compounds can modulate toxin proportions in the environment, averting the formation of detrimental concentrations by fostering the growth of MC-degrading bacteria. Consequently, comprehending the mechanisms by which various organic matter types influence MC persistence in water columns is paramount in elucidating the dynamics of toxin persistence within aquatic ecosystems. (Christiansen et al., 2008; Wei et al., 2021).

6.3. Persistence and distribution of MCs in the water column

Studies have shown that MCs can persist in the water column for a few days to several weeks, depending on the environmental conditions. Microbial degradation can be essential in reducing MC concentration in water bodies. Recent studies have demonstrated that MC-LR can be wholly degraded within seven days by a mixed microbial community obtained from a drinking water reservoir, starting with an initial concentration of $10 \mu\text{g MCs L}^{-1}$ (Santos et al., 2021).

However, other studies have demonstrated that MCs can exhibit remarkable stability, lasting up to 100 days at 40°C and pH 9 (Harada et al., 1996). Additionally, MCs are highly stable cyclic heptapeptides, showing resistance to enzymatic hydrolyses, such as trypsin. MCs remain resilient in natural lake water conditions, typically with pH levels of 9–10 and temperatures ranging from 25 to 30°C during the summer season. Furthermore, their structural integrity is maintained at pH 1–7 and 25°C , indicating their robustness even under less favorable environmental conditions (Harada et al., 1996; Tsuji et al., 1997). The vertical distribution of MCs in the water column can vary depending on the environmental conditions and the characteristics of the specific water body. Different variants of MC can exhibit different vertical distribution patterns in water columns. MC-LR and -RR are commonly detected at all depths, while MC-YR and -LA are often only detected in the surface layer (Braun and Bachofen, 2004; Ishikawa et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2012a). Studies have shown that MCs can be detected at various depths, ranging from 0 to 15 m (Ishikawa et al., 2002). However, under stratified conditions, MCs can significantly accumulate in the surface layer (Gardi et al., 2023). Overall, the transport and fate of cyanobacteria and MC in water columns are complex processes influenced by several physical and chemical factors. Understanding these processes is crucial for managing cyanobacterial blooms and reducing their impacts on human and animal health and aquatic ecosystems. Ongoing research is focused on developing strategies for predicting and managing cyanobacterial blooms, including early warning systems, nutrient management, and biological control methods.

7. Scaling up bioremediation strategies

Biotechnologies have gained significant attention in the field of water treatment, offering environmentally friendly, nature-based, and sustainable approaches for the removal of MCs from water sources. Several innovative methods, such as constructed wetlands, sand filtration, immobilized biofilm systems, bio-adsorbents, and the use of seaweeds, have been explored for their potential to mitigate MC contamination (Bavithra et al., 2020; Cheng et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2020; Zerrifi et al., 2021)c.

Constructed wetlands are engineered systems that combine specific plants, such as *Cyperus alternifolius* and *Phragmites australis*, and microbial communities to treat contaminated water. These wetlands function through a series of physical, chemical, and biological processes. The plants provide a physical barrier, promoting sedimentation and filtration of suspended particles, while the microbial communities play a crucial role in the degradation and transformation of MCs. Studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of constructed wetlands in achieving MCs removal rates ranging from 82 % to 92 % (Ahrenkiel Thyssen et al., 2023; Bavithra et al., 2020; Cheng et al., 2022b). The design and operation parameters of constructed wetlands, including hydraulic retention time, plant species selection, and wetland configuration, can influence their removal performance.

Sand filtration is a widely used physical filtration method for the removal of suspended particles and microorganisms, including MCs. The removal efficiency of sand filtration depends on various factors, such as the properties of the sand (e.g., grain size, porosity), the influent water quality, and the operating conditions. Studies have reported MC removal rates ranging from 70 % to 95 % using sand filtration (De Souza et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2020; Terin and Sabogal-Paz, 2019). The

performance of sand filters can be enhanced by optimizing design parameters, such as filter depth and backwashing frequency, as well as incorporating pre-treatment processes to prevent clogging and improve overall efficiency.

Filtration techniques, including granular activated carbon (GAC) filtration, have shown promise in removing MCs from water. GAC is a highly porous material with a large surface area that can adsorb MC molecules onto its surface. This adsorption mechanism is influenced by factors such as contact time, temperature, pH, and MC concentration in the water. Studies have reported MC removal rates reaching 94 % using GAC filtration (Fukumoto and Kuroda, 2019; Sorlini et al., 2019; Xiang et al., 2021). GAC filters can be designed as fixed-bed columns or used in conjunction with other treatment processes, such as pre-filtration or membrane filtration, to enhance overall removal efficiency.

Immobilized biofilm systems represent a promising biotechnology for MC removal. In these systems, microorganisms are immobilized on a support matrix, such as activated carbon, sand, or synthetic materials, forming biofilms that actively degrade MCs. The immobilization of the microorganisms enhances their stability, longevity, and catalytic activity. The removal performance of immobilized biofilm systems depends on factors such as biofilm composition, hydraulic retention time, and the initial MC concentration. Studies have reported MC removal rates reaching 92 % using immobilized biofilm systems (Kumar et al., 2019; Morón-López et al., 2020, 2019). Enhancing the microbial diversity within biofilms and optimizing system parameters can further improve their efficiency and resilience.

Bioadsorbents are effective tools for MC removal due to their ability to adsorb the toxin molecules onto their surfaces. Bioadsorbents for MC removal can be derived from various plant-based materials (El Bouaidi et al., 2020a, 2022). One commonly used plant source is coconut shell, which can be processed into activated carbon with excellent adsorption properties. Bamboo-based activated carbon, known for its high surface area and pore structure, is also effective for MC removal. Sawdust from different tree species, such as pine or eucalyptus, can be utilized as a plant-based bioadsorbent. Rice husk offers potential as a bioadsorbent, with both activated carbon and silica-based materials showing promise for MC adsorption. Corn cob-based bioadsorbents, typically in the form of activated carbon, have demonstrated effectiveness in MC removal. Additionally, waste materials like orange peels, banana peels, grapefruit peels, or seaweeds can be processed into bioadsorbents through appropriate techniques (El Bouaidi et al., 2020b; Pérez-Schirmer et al., 2019). The choice of plant-based material for bioadsorbents depends on factors such as availability, cost, adsorption capacity, and suitability for specific water treatment applications.

The biotechnologies discussed, including constructed wetlands, sand filtration, filtration techniques like GAC filtration, immobilized biofilm systems, and seaweed-based methods, offer promising solutions for MC removal. However, each technique has its own specific limitations and challenges. For example, constructed wetlands require a significant land area and careful monitoring. Sand filtration may face issues such as clogging and reduced filtration rates. Filtration techniques like GAC filtration need consideration of media characteristics and proper disposal. Immobilized biofilm systems require careful design and management to ensure optimal performance. Seaweed-based biotechnologies necessitate understanding growth requirements, bioaccumulation potential and ecological impacts. Economic feasibility, regulatory compliance, and public acceptance are also vital.

On top of these ecotechnologies, the MSL system stands out as a highly efficient and innovative method for MC-LR removal. One of the standout advantages of the MSL system lies in its cost-effectiveness, making it an attractive option for widespread application (Zhou et al., 2021). The engineering of the MSL system is inherently low-cost as it utilizes locally available materials, such as soil, wood charcoal, sawdust, and iron nails. These readily accessible components make the construction of the system easily achievable, contributing to its affordability and adaptability to various environmental settings.

Beyond its cost-effectiveness, the MSL system has demonstrated versatility in wastewater treatment. It has proven successful in sanitizing wastewater by efficiently removing pathogenic contaminants and organic pollutants. Notably, the MSL system achieved removal rates of 90 % for chemical oxygen demand (COD), total nitrogen, and total phosphorus (Maeng et al., 2021). This multifaceted approach not only addresses MC-LR but also extends its utility to broader water quality concerns, showcasing its potential as an integrated and comprehensive solution for water remediation (Aba et al., 2021).

The study of Aba et al. (2021) has shown that the MSL system exhibits tremendous promise, with MC removal rates reaching an impressive 99 %. The layered soil structures play a pivotal role in creating diverse microenvironments, optimizing conditions for microbial activities. This inherent design fosters synergistic effects among distinct microbial populations, contributing to the system's exceptional efficiency in degrading MCs (Mugani et al., 2022). The alternating treating layers and the permeable layers constructed with carefully chosen gravel sizes further prevent clogging issues, ensuring the sustained MSL functionality over long time periods.

Moreover, the durability of the MSL system adds to its advantages. Operating with minimal energy requirements and requiring less qualified labor for maintenance, the system proves to be a sustainable and long-lasting solution. In the case of domestic wastewater treatment, studies have indicated that the MSL system can function for up to a quarter of a century (Chen et al., 2009) without the need for material replacements. The materials used in the MSL system, after the end of their service life in water treatment, can be repurposed in agriculture, contributing to a circular and environmentally friendly approach.

8. Advancing research trends and identifying gaps in biological mc removal: insights from bibliometric analysis and concluding remarks

Managing cyanobacterial blooms and MC contamination requires an integrated approach that combines multiple management strategies. Biological technologies, such as biological filters, multi-soil-layering, and planted filters, have shown promise in managing these harmful algal blooms. However, there are still challenges and opportunities for future research and management. Therefore, in light of these findings, advancing our understanding of ecology, genetics, and physiology of MC-producing cyanobacteria and developing innovative and interdisciplinary approaches is critical for achieving sustainable solutions to this environmental and human health concern. Ultimately, the effective management of cyanobacterial blooms and MC contamination necessitates a holistic and collaborative effort from researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders.

Moreover, recent bibliometric analyses of MC research revealed that the majority of studies focused on the detection and toxicity of MCs, whereas fewer studies focused on their removal and the use of MC-degrading bacteria as a sustainable solution (Ding et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022b). Consequently, there is a pressing need for further research on developing and optimizing MC-degrading bacteria to remove MCs effectively.

Additionally, the bibliometric analysis uncovers that most MC removal studies were conducted in laboratory settings, with fewer studies carried out in field settings (Jeon et al., 2023; Li et al., 2020; Toporowska, 2022). This discrepancy indicates the necessity for additional research on the practical application of MCs-degrading bacteria in real-world settings, particularly in large-scale water treatment systems.

Furthermore, the bibliometric analysis exposes research gaps in the ecological roles, interactions, and removal methods of MC-degrading bacteria. Consequently, there is a pressing need for cost-effective and scalable applications in water treatment systems. Moreover, further studies are essential to investigate the impact of MC structural conformation on MC-degrading bacteria, as well as to unravel the underlying genetic mechanisms and develop specific strategies for efficient

removal. Highlighting the dominance of MC detection and toxicity research, the analysis underscores the necessity for studies focusing on MC removal. Notably, China and the USA are at the forefront of MC research, exhibiting many publications and citations.

In light of comprehensive bibliometric analysis, our study provides invaluable insights into the prevailing research trends and identifies research gaps within the domain of MC removal. Our analysis unequivocally underscores the pressing need for further research endeavors to advance the development and optimization of MC-degrading bacteria, thereby facilitating efficacious and sustainable MC elimination. Furthermore, the urgency for undertaking research endeavors focusing on cost-effective and scalable methodologies for implementing MC-degrading bacteria, including change-resilient strains in abiotically changing environments, remains imperative. Additionally, it is crucial to comprehend the intricate interplay between the structural conformation of MCs and their removal efficiency, necessitating meticulous investigations. The insights gleaned from our study are poised to chart the course for future research directions and foster fruitful collaborations within this field, ultimately culminating in the development of streamlined, resource-efficient solutions to effectively combat this pressing environmental quandary.

9. Perspectives on MC-Degrading bacteria for water treatment: advancements and challenges

MC contamination in global water sources is a pervasive and increasing issue, presenting substantial health and environmental risks. Within this context, research on MC-degrading bacteria emerges as a promising avenue for tackling this challenge (Dziga et al., 2020, 2017; Zhang et al., 2022a). Research perspectives, following our review, converge to highlight the necessity for practical, cost-efficient, and environmentally friendly solutions to address MC contamination and ensure the sustainability of water resources.

Enhancing the efficiency and expanding the scale of MC-degrading bacteria for large-scale water treatment plays a pivotal role in addressing harmful algal blooms and MC contamination. Implementing efficient and cost-effective methods is crucial for the practical application and monitoring of MC-degrading bacterial strains in real-world scenarios (Aba et al., 2021; Gouvea-Barros et al., 2019). There is an urgent demand to transition laboratory experiments into functional ecotechnologies for field applications and evaluate the scalability of these MC-degrading bacteria to ensure their adaptability across diverse contexts (Cheng et al., 2022b; Terin and Sabogal-Paz, 2019).

Studying MC biodegradation processes in innovative ecotechnologies like Multi-soil-layering (MSL) may further improve our understanding of MC removal efficiency (Aba et al., 2021; Mugani et al., 2022). Moreover, overall microbial communities in such systems should be investigated in detail considering the hydrological flow of water to elucidate the origin of the MC-degrading microbial community and their dynamics following MC exposure.

Considering the impact of climate change on MC prevalence and persistence in freshwater concerning their removal, investigating the effectiveness of MC-degrading bacteria under changing environmental conditions is essential to understanding the performances of ecotechnologies relying on these microorganisms in the MC removal processes (Cheng et al., 2022a; Moore et al., 2023). Identifying climate-resilient strains may offer a potential strategy to cope with variations induced by climate change and customize MC removal.

The application of specific MC-degrading bacteria targeting particular MC variants is crucial for engineering tailored ecotechnologies adapted for water treatment (Santos et al., 2021; Toporowska, 2022; Yang et al., 2018). Exploring the potential of these bacteria to address emerging toxic variants not effectively removed by current treatment methods is imperative in addressing evolving water quality challenges (Abbas et al., 2020; Gagala and Mankiewicz-Boczek, 2012; Zhan and Hong, 2022).

In developing countries, inadequate water treatment infrastructure exacerbates the risks posed by MC contamination (Salazar-Torres et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2008). Investigating the prevalence and impact of MC contamination in these regions is essential for understanding the scale of this global problem (Giaramida et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2008). Implementing MC-degrading bacteria as a low-cost and sustainable solution could offer significant socio-economic and environmental benefits, providing safer water sources for vulnerable communities (Terin and Sabogal-Paz, 2019).

10. Conclusion

- This study highlights the international collaborative efforts of researchers and the need for effective MC removal methods due to significant threats to human health, animal health, and the ecological balance of freshwater bodies.
- MC-degrading bacteria are emphasized as a promising solution for MC removal, and our review provides insights into the mechanisms employed by these bacteria for MC degradation and removal from water.
- The study recognizes challenges and limitations associated with using MC-degrading bacteria in real field conditions, emphasizing the need for further research to optimize bacterial strain selection to enhance MC biodegradation.
- We emphasize potential applications of MC-degrading bacteria, including low-cost ecotechnologies, e.g. multi-soil-layering (MSL), urging ongoing research to optimize their utilization in water treatment.
- Finally, the study calls for continued interdisciplinary research, employing advanced genomics and OMICS approaches, to identify and optimize MC-degrading bacteria, address knowledge gaps, and develop effective management strategies for controlling cyanobacterial blooms and subsequent MC contamination in water sources.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Richard Mugani: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft. **Fatima El Khalloufi:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **El Mahdi Redouane:** Software, Writing – review & editing. **Mohammed Haida:** Roseline Prisca **Aba:** Investigation. **Yasser Essadki:** Writing – review & editing. **Soukaina El Amrani Zerrifi:** Investigation. **Abdessamad Hejjaj:** Investigation, Methodology. **Naaila Ouazzani:** Writing – review & editing. **Alexandre Campos:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Hans-Peter Grossart:** Writing – review & editing. **Laila Mandi:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Vitor Vasconcelos:** . **Brahim Oudra:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Vitor Vasconcelos reports financial support, article publishing charges, and equipment, drugs, or supplies were provided by University of Porto Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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